

International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility Review Criteria for Endorsement of Standards and Best Practices

V1.0

Approved: July 10, 2018

Developed by: The Standards and Best Practices Committee
International Neuroinformatics Coordinating Facility

Area	Criteria
1: Open	1.1 Is the SBP covered under an open license so that it is free to implement and reuse by all interested parties (including commercial)? 1.2 What license is used? 1.3 Does the SBP follow open development practices? 1.4 Where and how are the code/documents managed?
2: FAIR	2.1 SBP uses/permits persistent identifiers where appropriate (F1) 2.2 SBP allows addition of rich metadata to research objects (F2) 2.3 SBP uses/permits addition of appropriate PIDs to metadata (F3) 2.4 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorization when required (A1.2) 2.5 SBP uses or allows the use of vocabularies that follow the FAIR principles (I2) 2.6 SBP includes/allows qualified links to other identifiers (I3) 2.7 Does the standard interoperate with other relevant standards in the same domain? (I) 2.8 Does the SBP provide citation metadata so its use can be documented and tracked? (R1.2)
3: Testing and implementation	3.1 Does the SBP have a reference implementation? 3.2 What tools are available for the SBP? 3.3 Are the tools and implementations covered under an open source license? 3.4 What is your assessment of the quality of the code/document?
4: Governance	4.1 Does the SBP have a clear description on who is maintaining the SBP and how decisions regarding its development are made?

	<p>4.2 Is the governing model document for maintenance and updates compatible with the INCF project governing model document and the open standards principles?</p> <p>4.3 Is the SBP actively supported by the community? If so, what is the evidence?</p> <p>4.4 Does the SBP provide tools for community feedback and support?</p>
<p>5: Adoption and use</p>	<p>5.1 Is there evidence of community use beyond the group that developed the SBP?</p> <p>5.2 Please provide some concrete examples of use, e.g., publications where the use of the SBP is cited; databases or other projects that have adopted the SBP</p> <p>5.3 Is there evidence of international use?</p>
<p>6: Stability and support</p>	<p>6.1 Who is responsible for maintaining the SBP?</p> <p>6.2 How is it currently supported?</p> <p>6.3 What is the plan for long term support?</p> <p>6.4 Are training and other supporting materials available?</p>
<p>7: Comparison</p>	<p>7.1 Are there other similar SBP's available?</p> <p>7.2 If yes, how do they compare on key INCF criteria?</p>